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"DAMPING PLATEAU" CREATED BY FATIGUE DAMAGE IN UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: In this presentation, a particular experiment has been designed to investigate the fatigue damage process in unidirectional (UD) fiber composites by the damping measurement. UD AS4 carbon fiber reinforced PEEK and epoxy as well as fiberglass-reinforced epoxy were considered. A “damping plateau” has been primarily detected from the damping dependence on fatigue cyclings in epoxy composites, and the mechanism of the “plateau” is discussed under the assumption of possible energy balance of fatigue load input and damage dissipation. The fatigue life of UD composite with a brittle epoxide matrix is better than that with a ductile thermoplastic matrix by using the same fibre reinforcement. The formation of transverse microcracks in epoxide matrix contributes to the energy dissipation under fatigue load, which seemingly improves the fatigue behaviour. Damping is recommended in the evaluation of damage process, which seems more sensitive than stiffness.

KEYWORDS: unidirectional (UD) fiber composite, tension-tension axial fatigue, fatigue damage, damping, and “damping plateau”

INTRODUCTION

Fibers are employed as reinforcement in brittle matrices, that results in a composite material with improved mechanical properties and enhanced resistance to crack growth. It might be thought that the strong fibers dominate the weak matrices in the fiber direction of composites, which is true for most static mechanical parameters such as modulus and strength, but for fatigue limitation. Resistance to crack growth in composites largely arises from two mechanisms in the static situation, the bridging or the trapping of the crack regarding to the reinforcement ahead of the crack tip. For the composite material under long duration fatigue or creep loads, another mechanism may contribute to the fracture resistance greatly due to energy dissipation in the matrix material^[1]. Under tensile cycling, the fatigue strength in fiber direction is significantly influenced by the comparatively weak polymer matrix. In fatigue of multidirectional laminates, the axial plies govern the fatigue life performance of the laminate if interpreted in terms of initial peak strain. The axial unidirectional (UD) ply constitutes the critical element, since it is more resistant to fatigue and has a larger strain to failure compared to off-axis UD plies. Therefore, the UD fibre composite is examined principally in more details to recognize the active fatigue damage mechanisms. Extensions to more general laminates can then be made on the basis of results from the UD composite.

Damping mechanisms in fiber composites can be of two categories, low-strain and high-strain damping^[2]. Low-strain damping is a domain of the polymeric matrix, which obeys linear viscoelastic relations. High-strains induce microcracks, which contribute for damping by

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friction. Fiber-matrix interface (interfacial region) condition strongly affects the mechanical properties of composite and quite affects its damping level also. Interfacial bonding in fiber reinforced composites can be considered to be weak, ideal or strong. Ideal interface plays the role of transferring loads and do not contribute to damping^[3]. Experimental studies carried out by a large number of research workers underline the effectiveness of damping as a measure of damage and cracks, and sufficient literature is available on crack or delaminating prediction and propagation in composites. However, there is still a need to quantify damage and its effect on damping of composite laminates and structures, and the theoretical work on damping behavior in delaminated composite structures is still not reported.

An interesting phenomenon has been well investigated in UD fibre composites. A brittle epoxy matrix composite exhibits higher fatigue resistance than that of a ductile thermoplastic (such as PEEK) matrix one in spite of the same fibre reinforcement, which can be attributed to the less dangerous nature of many microcracks formed in a brittle matrix compared to the few macrocracks in a ductile one during fatigue. This explanation is supported indirectly with some microstructural photographs, but is devoid of direct experimental evidence. In this presentation, a special experiment has been designed to investigate the process of fatigue cracks in UD fiber composites by the damping measurement. UD AS4 carbon fiber reinforced PEEK and epoxy, and fiberglass reinforced epoxy were considered. A fixed maximum strain (or stress) has been chosen for tension-tension axial fatigue which is below the fatigue *S-N* curve. Several specimens fatigued under this maximum strain (or stress) for various cyclings and stopped artificially before failure, were subjected to damping measurement. A “damping plateau” has been detected primarily from the damping/fatigue-cyclings relations in epoxide matrix composites, and the mechanism could be considered as the balance between fatigue input energy and amount of energy dissipation of the transverse microcracks. Damping also seems to be more sensitive than stiffness in the evaluation of damage process.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

1. Composite and samples

UD AS4 carbon fiber reinforced PEEK and epoxy and fiberglass reinforced epoxy were considered in this investigation. Table 1 gives their material components.

Table 1. Material components of composites

Fiber	Matrix	Fiber volume
Carbon (AS4)	PEEK	62%~63%
Carbon (AS4)	Epoxy	60%
Glass (E-glass)	Epoxy	72%~73%

The samples for tension-tension fatigue were cut with a span length of 250mm, a width of 10mm and a thickness of 2.0mm of AS4/PEEK, AS4/epoxy and fiberglass/epoxy. The fatigue samples were manufactured, cut, drilled and polished using standard techniques. 4 rectangular aluminum tabs were glued durably on the both two ends of a sample. The damping specimens were cut from fatigue specimens which experience different fatigue cyclings at a fixed maximum fatigue strain or stress. For torsion the samples had a length of 100mm, and width and thickness were kept the same as fatigue samples.

2. Apparatus

Tension-tension axial fatigue was performed using an Instron universal servo-hydraulic testing machine^[4]. A load cell was used to monitor the fatigue load and a uniaxial extensometer was used to measure the specimen strain. A computer data acquisition system

was used to record the load/strain data, the maximum and minimum displacements and numbers of fatigue cycles during fatigue tests. The fatigue tests were conducted at room temperature in stress or strain control and at a test frequency of 20Hz to avoid temperature effects, which may degrade the material properties otherwise. The fatigue load (or displacement) is applied in a sinusoidal form. When a maximum fatigue strain (or stress) has been chosen, the minimum strain at the 10% value of maximum one will be matched to meet the requirement of tension-tension fatigue.

The damping specimens were cut from fatigue specimens which experience different fatigue cyclings at a fixed maximum fatigue strain (or stress). For damping measurement, several methods can be applied. The loss factor $\tan\delta$ can be derived from the logarithmic decrement of successive amplitudes or oscillating velocities or by Fourier's analysis of the frequency spectrum of oscillations^[5-8]. Damping spectra and shear moduli were measured in a torsion pendulum at approx. 20Hz. The samples at the free end were connected to a disk of mass m for reducing frequency. The torsional vibrations were detected by reflecting a light beam on a mirror, which was fixed onto the sample. The velocity decrease with oscillations was determined photo-electronically, and used for calculating the loss factor, $\tan\delta$. The shear modulus G' was determined from the mean frequency. The accuracy of these devices was better than 3%.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

1. Carbon fibre Composites

Tension-tension $S-N$ fatigue strain life curves of UD AS4 carbon fiber composites with PEEK and epoxy matrices are given in figure 1. As we know that ductile thermoplastic PEEK has better mechanical and fatigue behaviour than a brittle thermoset epoxide resin. The static tensile failure strains ($N=0$) of both composites are similar which are around the value of 1.57% because of fibre domination of this parameter and both composites have similar fibre volume. But the fatigue strain life ($N=10^7$) for AS4/PEEK is only 0.57%, which is much poorer than that for AS4/epoxy (0.84%) shown in figure 1. For understanding the mechanism of this interesting phenomenon, an extraordinary experiment has been designed to investigate the process of fatigue cracks. A fixed maximum strain of 0.9% (dot line in figure 1) has been chosen which is below the fatigue $S-N$ curves of both AS4/PEEK and AS4/epoxy. Several specimens have been fatigued at this maximum strain for scheduled fatigue cyclings - 10^0 , 10^1 , 10^3 , 5×10^3 , 10^4 , 2×10^4 , 10^5 , 5×10^5 , 10^6 , 2×10^6 for AS4/epoxy and 10^0 , 10^1 , 10^3 , 5×10^3 , 10^4 , 2×10^4 for AS4/PEEK respectively before their fatigue failure. And then the specimens have been cut in the length of 100mm for damping measurement.

Table 2 Damping of UD AS4/PEEK and AS4/epoxy in various fatigue levels.

Fatigue Cyclings N	Damping (%)	
	AS4/epoxy	AS4/PEEK
10^0	0.48	0.34
10^1	0.45	0.38
10^3	0.53	0.42
5×10^3	0.52	0.45
10^4	0.62	0.59
2×10^4	0.73	1.38
10^5	0.80	-
5×10^5	0.78	-
10^6	0.82	-
2×10^6	1.47	-

Fig. 1 Tension-tension fatigue life of UD carbon fiber composites under loading parallel to fiber direction.

Fig. 2 Influence of fatigue cracks on longitudinal torsion damping of UD carbon fiber composites.

Damping (internal friction), which is an important parameter related to energy dissipation for composite materials under dynamic force, has been summarized in table 2 and drawn in figure 2 versus fatigue cyclings. Increase in damping is reported due to matrix cracks, broken fibers and interface debonding which is more sensitive to these damages than stiffness. For AS4/PEEK in figure 2, it can be seen that damping increases slightly from the fatigue cyclings of 10^0 to 5×10^3 because of the high crack resistance of ductile thermoplastic PEEK. From 10^4 to 2×10^4 , which approaches to the fatigue life of AS4/PEEK, damping increases significantly because of the debonding of interface and fatigue failure of the composite. The phenomenon is different for AS4/epoxy. After a slight increase from 10^0 to 5×10^3 cyclings and a considerable jump from 10^4 to 2×10^4 , the damping of AS4/epoxy presents a “plateau” from 2×10^4 to 10^5 at the absolute value of 8×10^{-3} . Afterward, according to the further process of fatigue, damping in epoxy composite significantly increased until fatigue failure. Different damping/fatigue-cycling relations were produced undeniably by diverse fatigue mechanism for carbon fibre reinforced PEEK and epoxide matrix.

2. Fiberglass Composites

Figure 3 gives the tension-tension fatigue stress life curve of UD fiberglass reinforced epoxy. The static tensile failure stress ($N=0$) dominated by fibre of the composite is up to 1,100MPa and the fatigue stress life ($N=10^7$) is only 120MPa. For investigating the dependence of damping with fatigue cyclings, a fixed maximum stress of 350MPa (dot line in figure 3) has been chosen under the fatigue $S-N$ curve. Specimens have been fatigued at this maximum stress at scheduled fatigue cyclings of 10^0 , 5×10^3 , 10^4 , 2×10^4 , 5×10^4 , 10^5 and 2×10^5 respectively and the results of damping and shear modulus measured by torsion pendulum are given in table 3 and figure 4.

In figure 4, a “damping plateau” of UD fiberglass/epoxy has been observed in the damping/fatigue-cycling relation, which is similar like carbon-fibre/epoxy in figure 2. After a slight increase from 10^0 to 5×10^3 cyclings and a considerable jump from 5×10^3 to 10^4 , the damping presents a “plateau” from 10^4 to 10^5 at the value around 8×10^{-3} to 9×10^{-3} , then again significantly increases with further fatigue process until failure. However, the shear modulus presents a slight dependence with fatigue process unless near failure, which means that modulus decrease are less sensitive than the damping increase according to fatigue damages of matrix cracks, broken fibers and interface debonding in UD fibre composites.

Table 3 Damping and shear modulus of UD fiberglass/epoxy in various fatigue levels.

Fatigue Cyclings N	Damping (%)	Shear Modulus (GPa)
10^0	0.53	4.60
5×10^3	0.62	5.49
10^4	0.85	4.62
2×10^4	0.79	5.03
5×10^4	0.79	4.56
10^5	0.88	4.70
2×10^5	2.12	3.01

DISCUSSIONS

Fatigue damage mechanisms are diagramed in figure 5 for both brittle epoxy and tough thermoplastic matrices UD composites under loading parallel to fiber direction^[9]. Fibre breakage (figure 5a) occurs at stresses exceeding the strength of the weakest fibre, which may happen at the lower fatigue cyclings of each kind of fibre-reinforced composites. An isolated fibre break causes shear stress concentration at the interface around the tip of the broken fibre. The interface may then fail, leading to debonding of the fibre from the surrounding matrix.

Fig. 3 Fatigue life of UD fiberglass/epoxy under loading parallel to fiber direction.

Fig. 4 Influence of fatigue cracks on longitudinal torsion damping and shear modulus of UD fiberglass composites.

Fig. 5 Fatigue damage mechanisms in unidirectional composites under loading parallel to fiber direction; (a) fiber breakage, interfacial debonding; (b) matrix cracking for brittle epoxy; (c) interfacial shear fatigue failure for tough thermoplastic matrix.

The debonded area acts as a stress concentration site for the longitudinal tensile stress. The magnified tensile stress may exceed the fracture stress of the brittle matrix (such as epoxy) leading to several transverse microcracks as shown in figure 5b. These transverse cracks will definitely contribute to damping. Accompanying the numerous of transverse microcracks, the measured damping will also increase significantly. The transverse microcracks will also contribute to the energy dissipation under fatigue load, which improve the fatigue behaviour of epoxide matrix composites. While a balance between the fatigue energy input and the amount of energy dissipation due to transverse microcracks is reached, the “damping plateau” may form. When this energy balance of fatigue input and damage dissipation is broken under the further fatigue process, damping significantly increases again and the composite trends to failure.

The failure stress of a tough thermoplastic matrix (such as PEEK) is high and the matrix transverse cracks are not easy to be formed. The shear stress concentration site under such a shear fatigue situation (as in figure 5c) may propagate a macrocrack under the further fatigue process which is more dangerous than transverse microcracks in brittle matrix. Additionally, ductile thermoplastic matrices tend to form longitudinal cracks as shown in figure 5c, which reduce the shear transfer between fibers. These could lead the fatigue failure of the UD composite. In the damping dependence on fatigue cyclings of AS4/PEEK, damping keeps at a low level initially because of less transverse cracks, afterward increases significantly while longitudinal cracks form and composite is inclined to sudden fatigue failure.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A special experiment has been successfully designed to investigate the process of tension-tension axial fatigue damage in UD fiber composites by the damping measurement. The formation of transverse microcracks in brittle epoxide matrix composites contributes to the energy dissipation under fatigue load, which improves the fatigue behaviour of composites. A “damping plateau” has been primarily detected from the damping dependence on fatigue cyclings in these composites, which could be used for the explanation why fatigue life is better for a brittle epoxide matrix than that for a ductile thermoplastic with same fibre reinforcement.
2. The mechanism of the “damping plateau” formation in epoxide matrix composites is discussed under the assumption of possible energy balance between fatigue input and damage dissipation.

3. Damping is recommended in the evaluation of damage process in composite materials, which seems more sensitive than stiffness.

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